

**MECHANISMS TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF SCIENTIFIC
EDUCATION IN THE SYSTEM OF SPECIAL EDUCATION
THE MECHANISM OF INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF CLASSES
SCIENTIFIC EDUCATION IN THE SYSTEM
SPECIAL IMAGES**

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the mechanisms of effective teaching of science lessons to younger students with hearing impairments and the corresponding corrective approaches. In this state, they consider the mechanism of effective teaching of science lessons to younger students with hearing impairment and the correct corrective approach.

KEYWORDS: *Nature , Object , Event , Process , Special Live Broadcast Technique And Lifeless Nature , Thinking , Special Education , Hearing Perception , Aesthetics Feeling , Intonation , Synthesis .*

: Nature, Object, Phenomenon, Process, Special Methodology, Living Nature, Thinking, Special Idea, Auditory Perception, Aesthetic Feeling, Intonation, Synthesis, Inanimate Nature.

INTRODUCTION

The basis for the comprehensive education of hearing-impaired schoolchildren is the formation of a scientific worldview in them. Natural science occupies an important place in the implementation of this task in the primary grades. The study of this subject enriches the personal experience of school children with hearing impairment at an early age, helps them to accumulate knowledge about the phenomena and processes occurring in the animate and inanimate nature around us, develop speech, increase vocabulary, improve their hearing and develop abilities.

Perfect knowledge of the special methodology of teaching natural science allows you to properly organize the education of children with hearing impairments of primary school age. The methodology equips special school teachers with the theory of pedagogical science and allows them to acquire pedagogical skills.

It is necessary to take a different look at the use of different teaching methods when disclosing the content of educational materials. When choosing one or another method, the teacher should take into account that such a choice of methods provides a solution to the problems of developmental education, activates the cognitive activity of students with hearing impairments and at the same time organizes remedial education. Therefore, at a boarding school, natural science classes for children with hearing impairments, practical activities, conversations, emotional stories, features of using independent work: simple analysis and synthesis, comparison and generalization to determine indicators between natural phenomena should be mandatory components of the work. All this develops speech, thinking, memory, imagination of students with hearing impairment, increases vocabulary.

Visual aids and technical aids are required, as well as an excursion, to influence the acquisition of science concepts by students with hearing impairment. In the process of teaching natural science to deaf and hard of hearing students, the foundations of a scientific worldview are formed (the teacher consistently conveys the materiality of natural objects and phenomena, their interdependence, characterizes the constant changes occurring in nature). Fosters love for nature, an aesthetic sense, a careful attitude towards it.

On the basis of regular study of the world surrounding hearing-impaired school children, it is necessary to form in them a holistic view of nature, their place and the natural wealth of the whole country. Students should get to know how people use the natural resources of our country in their work activities. It is very important to show children that human labor is closely connected with nature. According to these requirements, provide students with accurate knowledge of living and inanimate nature; to teach to understand their interdependence; equipping with training and skills to conduct observations in nature; involvement in human labor activity aimed at the rational use of nature and the preservation of its wealth; The above goal is the educational goal of teaching science. Learning objectives used in teaching science in a school for deaf and hard of hearing children include teaching students theoretical knowledge and practical skills according to the curriculum.

It is known that a primary defect leads to a secondary defect. The development of cognitive activity of a child with hearing impairment has a direct and indirect impact. According to the Russian psychologist L.I. Ivanov, "speech is closely connected with thinking. Man cannot think without speech, without linguistic means. If there is no thought, speech and language are impossible." As can be seen from Ivanov's opinion above, speech and thought processes are closely related to the mental development of a person.

I.M. Solovieva, L.I. Tigranova: the lag in the development of speech is due to negative factors; Perception of the environment, memorization of visual and verbal material contributes to the development of mental operations. What kind of hearing loss does the child have (i.e. at what age) and to what extent affects the development of his mental operations.

According to scientists, a healthy seven-year-old child has a well-formed mindset.

So: concepts are a process of thinking. Thus, the formation of scientific ideas in hearing-impaired students is closely related to the development of their mental operations. Because it is determined that the formation and better development of speech in younger students with hearing impairments, compared to healthy students, have a somewhat later idea of the world. That is,

hearing-impaired schoolchildren lag behind speech and higher cognitive processes. Primary school students with hearing impairment cannot compare, analyze, synthesize, and generalize, draw conclusions. Students with hearing impairments are mainly taught from exhibits and specific materials. Primary school students with hearing impairments think for a long time in a figurative-visual type of thinking until they master verbal communication. It was seen that the ideas of the hearing impaired are formed very slowly.

In many cases, students with hearing impairments have difficulty changing the science curriculum. Concepts formed in the lesson on one topic do not develop further and are not connected with other concepts. In particular, the formation of natural science concepts occurs in certain methodological conditions. Various types of objects and visual materials in the primary teaching of concepts:

- Logical questions;
- Tables;
- Scheme;
- Pictures;
- Abstract type card - tasks;
- Digital programming tasks;
- programmed didactic cards;
- Game exercises on the topic;
- Educational games.

1. Teacher questions play an important role in preparing students for active thinking. At the lessons of natural science, when repeating the text of the textbook, it is necessary to ask questions that require analysis, synthesis, and generalization.

For example: Why is there no snow in summer?

What is the similarity between the nature of the steppe and the desert?

Why does the fetus not ripen at work?

2. A set of questions that develop concepts includes comparing natural objects with their images on the board, creating diagrams, combining them with pictures and herbariums on the board.

Using the table, students compare the external signs of plants and animals to determine how they are adapted to life in various natural conditions.

3. A similar exercise is carried out to fill in the tables posted by the teacher. Tables can be filled in in class and at home for comparison and generalization. Comparative tables are used in financial work in the classroom, in the corner of wildlife, in the school educational and experimental field.

4. Thesis type card - tasks.

On a certain numbered card, the names of natural science objects (plants, animals) are given.

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